

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5846768>

УДК 616.155.194.125

DIABETES MELLITUS IN THALASSAEMIC PATIENTS

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Annotation: Thalassemia is a genetic disorder involving the underproduction of the globin chains of hemoglobin. In patients with Thalassemia, uncontrolled iron overload has serious clinical consequences with considerable morbidity and mortality. Complications include liver damage, cardiac disease, and endocrine dysfunction. Type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM) is a frequent complication in patients with beta-thalassemia. It is believed to be due to the damage inflicted by the iron overload of the pancreatic beta cells. The aim of this research is to investigate the latest findings from studies on the relationship between diabetes and thalassemia. The research was conducted in five databases (PubMed, National Center for Biotechnology Information NCBI, Scopus, Wiley online library, and Google Scholar) from the time of inception until December 2021.

Keywords: β -thalassemia (β -thal), β -thalassemia major, iron overload, diabetes mellitus, diabetes

САХАРНЫЙ ДИАБЕТ У ТАЛАССЕМИЧЕСКИХ БОЛЬНЫХ

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Аннотация: Талассемия – это генетическое заболевание, связанное с недостаточной продукцией глобиновых цепей гемоглобина. У пациентов с талассемией неконтролируемая перегрузка железом имеет серьезные клинические последствия со значительной заболеваемостью и смертностью. Осложнения включают повреждение печени, сердечные заболевания и эндокринную дисфункцию. Сахарный диабет 1 типа (СД) является частым осложнением у пациентов с β -талассемией. Считается, что это связано с повреждением бета-клеток поджелудочной железы, вызванным перегрузкой железом. Целью данного исследования является изучение последних результатов исследований взаимосвязи между диабетом и талассемией. Исследование проводилось в пяти базах данных (PubMed, Национальный центр биотехнологической информации NCBI, Scopus, онлайн-библиотека Wiley и Google Scholar) с момента создания до декабря 2021 года.

Ключевые слова: β -талассемия (β -thal), большая β -талассемия, перегрузка железом, сахарный диабет, диабет

1. Introduction.

Thalassemia is a serious genetic blood disorder in which the body makes an abnormal form of hemoglobin. Thalassemia is inherited, meaning that at least one of your parents must be a carrier of the disorder. It's caused by either a genetic mutation or a deletion of certain key gene fragments [1].

Patients with beta-thalassemia major were kept alive by repeated blood transfusion and iron chelation. They are exposed to the hazards of iron overload and infections [2]. Chronic iron overload results in cardiac and hepatic dysfunction as well as several endocrine abnormalities, especially the development of type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM) [3-5]. Prevalence of diabetes among thalassemia patients has been reported to range from 20-30 % of adult patients with β -thalassemia worldwide, and has been considered to be responsible for the high rate of morbidities [6]. The mechanism that leads to DM in Thalassemia is multifactorial. Some regard iron-induced pancreas cytotoxicity as the most significant contributor.

While this was a traditional idea, a new hypothesis suggests the exhaustion of beta-pancreatic cells subsequent to a chronic period of hyperinsulinemia to be involved in the development of DM in Thalassemia [7].

Although insulin deficiency, secondary to pancreatic islet iron deposition, has been considered the principal cause of the abnormalities in glucose metabolism observed in Thalassemias [8-10], other studies have reported hyperinsulinemia with oral glucose tolerance testing, suggesting a role for insulin resistance in mediating these metabolic abnormalities [11-12]. Hemosiderosis, liver infections, and genetic factors seemed to be crucial in the development of diabetes [13-14]. Therefore, in this article, our goal is to summarize the current evidence about the relationship between thalassemia and diabetes.

2. Materials and methods.

2.1. Search strategy.

A review was performed of some published research articles from (Egypt, Syria, Indonesia, Italy, China, and Iran) on β -thal patients and the possibility to develop diabetes mellitus. Five literature databases (PubMed, National Center for Biotechnology Information NCBI, Scopus, Wiley online library, and Google Scholar) were searched to include the relevant articles published in English. We used the “Beta Thalassemia” search term in combination with one of these terms: “diabetes”, “DM” or “diabetes mellitus”. For example “Beta Thalassemia” and “diabetes”.

2.2. Study selection.

Research articles were selected based on the following selection criteria: (1) original research articles published in scientific journals. (2) Studies that included studies investigating the prevalence of diabetes among thalassemia patients. Articles that failed to meet any of the inclusion criteria were excluded.

3. Results.

The first study is from Ain Shams University in Egypt, research about the prevalence and risk factors for diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) in transfusion-dependent Egyptian beta-thalassemia patients and the possible role of genotyping in diabetes development was done by Khalifa AS et al, in 2004 in Hematology/Oncology Clinic, Children's Hospital, the number of patients was 56, ages ranged between 10-31 (mean age= 15.9 \pm 5.7 yr), including 48 thalassemia major and eight thalassemia intermedia; compared to 15 age- and sex-matched controls. The study shows that 10.4 % of beta-thalassemia major patients developed DM and 14.6 % had IGT. Ethnic variations are frequently reported on the prevalence and complications of DM in beta-thalassemia patients. Ramachandran et al [15] reported a prevalence of 12.1 % and 14 % for DM and IGT, respectively, in India. Similar results were reported by Desancitis et al [16] in Italy, whereas, a lower prevalence was found in Saudi thalassemic patients (6 % for DM) compared to other ethnic groups [17].

Khalifa AS et al, found that the fasting plasma glucose, 2-h post-load plasma glucose, and C-peptide showed a positive correlation with serum ferritin levels, suggesting that the degree of iron overload is responsible for the insulin resistance. Also, the significant positive correlation between fasting and 2-h post-load plasma glucose with the disease duration suggests that the duration of exposure of the patient to chronic iron overload is important [18]. The treatment for thalassemia may lead to a decreased hepatic insulin clearance, resulting in hyperinsulinemia and compensatory insulin resistance [19]. The significant positive correlation of C-peptide and BMI may also suggest the role of obesity in the development of insulin resistance [18].

Chronic hepatitis C may play a role in the development of abnormal glucose tolerance among beta-thalassemia patients. Diabetes has been observed to develop shortly after an episode of acute viral hepatitis in Thalassemia patients [8], and chronic hepatitis C infection was considered to have a diabetogenic effect. None of the patients in this study had acute hepatitis, but chronic hepatitis C was found to be a risk factor for abnormal glucose tolerance in them (100 % of patients) [18].

Another study from Al-Sham Private University – Syria, research on Investigation of Fasting Glucose and Glucose Tolerance in Syrian Beta Thalassemia Major Patients was done by Shoujaa A et al, (2021), in Thalassemia Center in Damascus, the number of patients was 35, ages ranged between 15-35 years, with a mean age of 22.5 Years. The mean weight was 51.9 Kg for males and 48.7 Kg for females. The mean height was 161.3 cm for males and 150.2 cm for females. The mean BMI was 19.7 Kg/m² for males and 21.7 Kg/m² for females. The mean concentration of hemoglobin was 7.1g/dl for males and 7g/dl for females. The percentage of taking chelators was 80 %, while the percentage of non-users was 20 %. The percentage of patients who suffer from hereditary diabetes is 46 %, and 56 % did not suffer. Normal fasting glucose concentration was 40 % of patients and the same percentage was for prediabetes patients, while diabetic patients were 20 %. Normal glucose tolerance was 57 % of patients and the percentage of prediabetes patients was 37 %, while diabetic patients were 6 % [20]. They found that there is no correlation between (IFG, IGT) and (risk factors, BMI, blood transfusion), it may be attributed to the fact that the majority of patients are under normal weight or in the lower limits of normal weight due to lack of nutrition, the insufficient frequency of blood, and that the transferred iron accumulates in other parts of the body. When studying the variable iron chelators the study concluded that there is a correlation with IGT, it is maybe attributed to irregularity in taking chelators by the patients [20].

In a similar study at Zahedan University in Iran, research on factors affecting diabetes in thalassemia patients was done by Jahantigh et al in 2013 in Ali Asghar Hospital for blood transfusion, the number of patients was 384, ages

ranged between 10 and 30 years, with an average of 7.17-9.14 and an IGT ratio 6.3 % and the DM ratio is 15.1 % [21]. When studying the relationship with the iron chelator deferoxamine, they found that 11 % of the patients suffer from diabetes, so the study concluded that there was no relationship with the iron chelator deferoxamine, but they noticed that the concentration of sugar tolerance increased when taking the iron chelator deferral. They also noticed that with advancing age, the risk of diabetes developing increases [20].

In 2021 in Faculty of Medicine Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia, a research to detect Glycated Albumin as Marker for Early Hyperglycemia Detection in the adolescent with β Thalassemia Major was done by Candrarukmi D, et al. in Dr. Moewardi Regional General Hospital, the number of patients was 53, aged between 9 to 18 years. Based on the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) levels, the prevalence of DM was 1.9 % and that of prediabetes was 7.5 % in the 53 patients with β Thalassemia major treated at the Dr. Moewardi Regional General Hospital. These prevalence rates are consistent with previous findings showing that the prevalence of DM in β Thalassemia major varied from 2 % to 9.4 % and that the prevalence of impaired glucose tolerance ranged from 4.4 % to 30 %. In this study, all FBG (fasting blood glucose) levels were within the normal limits. However, another study reported that the frequency of fasting blood sugar disorders in patients with β thalassemia major aged 10–20 years was 14.8 % [22]. A study in Chinese children reported that ages older than 10 years and ferritin levels higher than 2500 np/mL were associated with abnormalities in glucose metabolism in patients with β Thalassemia major [23]. The median GA value was 10.9 % (range: 7.6-12.4 %). No significant difference in the GA value was observed in terms of gender ($p = 0.771$) and nutritional status ($p = 0.192$) (Table 3). A weak positive correlation was observed between GA and age ($r = 0.045$, $p = 0.749$), but this correlation was not statistically significant. The study showed that GA value cannot be used as a screening tool for hyperglycemia detection in children with β Thalassemia major [24].

Moreover, insulin resistance accompanied by hyperinsulinism conditions in order to maintain blood glucose homeostasis in patients with β Thalassemia major may occur even though the glucose tolerance is normal [25]. In the event the glucose tolerance is impaired, a patient may display insulin resistance accompanied by decreased insulin secretion. Given that impaired glucose tolerance and insulin resistance occur before the onset of DM, early detection of prediabetes and DM is important.

4. Conclusion.

This work highlights the latest findings from studies on the relationship between diabetes and thalassemia.

Abnormal glucose metabolism is common in β Thalassemia major patients with chelation therapy and multiple transfusions, which are attributable to impaired β cells' function and increased insulin resistance.

The degree of iron overload is responsible for insulin resistance as fasting plasma glucose, 2-hour plasma glucose and C-peptide were found to be positively correlated with serum ferritin levels.

Chronic hepatitis C and acute viral hepatitis may be due to abnormal glucose tolerance among beta-thalassemia patients.

GA value cannot be used as a screening tool for hyperglycemia detection, it is necessary to search for other alternative markers for the detection of hyperglycemia in patients with β thalassemia.

Patients who had serum ferritin of 2000 micrograms per liter and more had an increase in their glucose tolerance concentration. The risk of developing diabetes in thalassemia patients increases with age.

Well, though, more studies are necessary to determine the actual picture of β -thal and its relation to diabetes.

Bibliography

[1] Marengo-Rowe A.J. The thalassemias and related disorders. / A.J. Marengo-Rowe. // Proc (Bayl Univ Med Cent). – 2007. № 20. 27-31 p.

[2] Survival and causes of death in thalassemia major. / M.G. Zurlo, P. De Stefano, C. Borgna-Pignatti et al. // Lancet. – 1989. № 2. 27-30 p.

[3] Saudek C.D. Abnormal glucose tolerance in β -thalassemia major. / C.D. Saudek, R.M. Hemm, C.M. Peterson. // Metabolism. – 1977. № 16. 43-52 p.

[4] Gabutti V. Results of long-term iron chelation therapy. / V. Gabutti, A. Piga. // Acta Haematol. – 1996. № 95. 26-36 p.

[5] Survival and disease complications in thalassemia major. / C. Borgna-Pignatti, S. Rugolloto, P. De Stefano et al. // Ann N Y Acad Sci. – 1998. № 850. 227-231 p.

[6] The ICET-A Recommendations for the Diagnosis and Management of Disturbances of Glucose Homeostasis in Thalassemia Major Patients. / V. De Sanctis, A.T. Soliman, H. Elsedfy, S.A. Yaarubi, N. Skordis, et al. // Mediterr J Hematol Infect Dis. – 2016. № 8(1). e2016058.

[7] Bazi A. Diabetes Mellitus in Thalassemia Major Patients: A Report from the Southeast of Iran. / A. Bazi. // Journal of clinical and diagnostic research. – 2017. doi:10.7860/JCDR/2017/24762.9806.

[8] Abnormal glucose tolerance in transfusion dependant beta thalassemia. / JPS CHER, et al. // Diabetes Care. – 2001. № 24. 850-854 p.

[9] Interleukin 1-beta, tumour necrosis factor-alpha, islet-cell antibody and insulin secretion in children with thalassemia major on long-term blood

transfusion. / A. El-Nawawy, A.T. Soliman, O. El-Azzouni et al. // *J Trop Pediatr.* – 1996. № 42. 362-364 p.

[10] The possible role of autoimmunity in the pathogenesis of diabetes in b-thalassemia major. / L. Monge, S. Pinach, L. Caramellino, M.T. Bertero, A. Dall'omo, Q. Carta. // *Diabetes Metab.* – 2001. 27 (2 Part 1). 149-154 p.

[11] Insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia in patients with thalassemia major treated by hypertransfusion. / P.A. Merkel, D.C. Simonson, S.A. Amiel et al. // *N Engl J Med.* – 1988. № 318. 809-814 p.

[12] Berdousi H. Glucose disturbances of regulation with glibenclamide in thalassemia. / H. Berdousi, C. Kattamis. // *J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.* – 1998. № 11 (Suppl. 3). 871-878 p.

[13] Incidence of endocrine complications and clinical disease severity related to genotype analysis and iron overload in patients with beta-thalassemia. / C.E. Jansen, S.M. Tuck, J. Old et al. // *Eur J Haematol.* – 1997. № 59. 76-81 p.

[14] De Sanctis V. The development of diabetes mellitus and chronic liver disease in long-term chelated beta thalassaemic patients. / V. De Sanctis, G. D'ascola, B. Wonke. // *Postgrad Med J.* – 1986. № 62. 831-836 p.

[15] High prevalence of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance in India: National Urban Diabetes Survey. / A. Ramachandran, C. Snehalatha, A. Kapur et al. // *Diabetologia.* – 2001. № 44. 1094-1101 p.

[16] Insulin dependent diabetes in thalassemia. / V. De Sanctis, M.G. Zurlo, E. Senesi et al. // *Arch Dis Child.* – 1988. № 63. 58-62 p.

[17] Diabetes mellitus in children suffering from beta-thalassemia. / M.A. El-Hazmi, A. Al-Swailem, I. Al-Fawaz, A.S. Warsey, A. Al-Swailem. // *J Trop Pediatr.* – 1994. № 40. 261-267 p.

[18] Abnormal glucose tolerance in Egyptian beta-thalassaemic patients: possible association with genotyping. / A.S. Khalifa, M. Salem, E. Mounir, M.M. El-Tawil, M. El-Sawy, M.M. Abd Al-Aziz. // *Pediatric Diabetes.* – 2004. № 5. 126-132 p.

[19] Serum ferritin as a component of the insulin resistance syndrome. / J.M. Fernandez-Real, W. Ricart-Engel, E. Arroyo et al. // *Diabetes Care.* – 1998. № 21. 62-68 p.

[20] Investigation of Fasting Glucose and Glucose Tolerance in Syrian Beta Thalassemia Major Patients. / L. Mukhallati, M. Farah, A. Shoujaa. // *J Comm Med and Pub Health Rep* 2(9). – 2021.

[21] Therapeutic Action Guide for Thalassemia Patients, Syria, Syrian Ministry Of Health. – 2021. 98 p.

[22] Wirawan R. Diabetes mellitus in b-thalassemia major patients. / R. Wirawan, S. Setiawan, S. Kusnandar, B.G. Munthe. // *Med J Indones.* – 2003. № 12. 87-93 p.

[23] Prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Chinese children with thalassemia major. / Y. Liang, R. Bajoria, Y. Jiang, H. Su, H. Pan, N. Xia, et al.. // Trop Med Int Health. – 2017. № 22. 716-24 p.

[24] Glycated Albumin for Hyperglycemia Detection in Thalassemia. / D. Candrarukmi, et al. – 2021. № 13(3). 281-8 p.

[25] Sactis V.D. Chapter 8: Endocrine disease. / V.D. Sactis, N. Skordis, A.T. Solirhan. // In: Cappellini MD, Cohen A, Porter J, editors. Guidelines for the Management of Transfusion Dependent Thalassaemia (TDT). 3rd ed. – Strevolos: Thalassemia International Federation, 2014. 151-4 p.

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Поступила в редакцию 21.11.2021

Принята к публикации 5.12.2021

Для цитирования:

Sleiman M. Diabetes mellitus in thalassaemic patients // Инновационные научные исследования. 2021. № 12-1(14). С. 19-26. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>